

IMPETUS 4 CHANGE

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Impetus4Change Quality Assurance Protocols (KPIs)

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Responsible	Stefan Sobolowski
Author	Stefan Sobolowski
Summary	This deliverable codifies the adoption of quality assurance protocols KPIs for the project by the Scientific Steering Committee. These KPIs will be revisited yearly and will ensure the project is hitting its targets. Report back on these KPIs will occur in M25 and M40. They are also included in the project manual (D8.1). It is a living document and will be updated as necessary.

**Zenodo repository for I4C
open access documents**

[Impetus4Change Community](https://zenodo.org/communities/impetus4change)

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1 Summary

To manage risks and ensure that I4C achieves its objectives and realizes its impacts we define six KPIs which will help guide the project management team (the SSC) in its assessment of the project's progress (how a KPI is measured is noted in the righthand column). They will be assessed throughout the project (during e.g., annual project meetings) and refined and updated as needed. Two separate reports on the KPIs are planned (M25 and M40), and they will be included in the project periodic reporting to the EC.

It is a living document, and will be updated as necessary (e.g., updates in contacts, folder links, procedures, etc.) or as further needs for clarifications and guidance appear throughout the project.

Table 1. Impetus4Change Quality Assurance Protocols (project-level KPIs).

KPI	Description	Measures
K1	Measure the physical readiness of the approaches and newly developed outputs in WPs 2-5 through thorough quality assessment using relevant metrics for each area (e.g., skill scores, comparisons to high density observations, process evaluation, representation of extremes, impacts and uncertainty and satisfying assumptions underpinning generations of seamless information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific output (e.g., peer-reviewed papers) Evaluations/intermediate assessments
K2	Measure the fitness-for-purpose of I4C results from fundamental science (WPs 2-5) through to implementation and action (WP1,6); this overlaps with K1 and includes both surveys of stakeholders and scientists on whether I4C is producing actionable information as well as quantitative assessments (Quantitative and qualitative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveys of I4C scientists and stakeholders (undertaken in the course of the relevant work packages)
K3a	Evaluate the co-production processes in the project, specifically in the Demonstrators and in the Klimathons, conducted through an internal survey of I4C scientists as well as a survey of local stakeholders from the Demonstrators (surveys of co-production with stakeholders are already scheduled as part of the WP6 work plan) (Qualitative).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-evaluation task team reporting and co-evaluation documentation
K3b	Assessment of depth & quality of stakeholder, user interactions within demonstrators and elsewhere such as the knowledge networks in WP1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # meetings and/or interactions (quant.) Examples of direction/input from stakeholders and/or users (qual.) # multiplier opportunities/contacts (quant.)
K4	Enhance early career development within the project by elevating at least two I4C postdocs to lead WP tasks and encourage early career scientists to lead participation in Klimathons, conference sessions, Communication Dissemination Exploitation (CDE)(Qualitative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elevate two I4C early career scientists to leadership roles (e.g., task lead) Ensure early career scientist involvement in planning/participating in Klimathons, conference sessions, CDE activities

K5	Ensure engagement and efficacy of CDE with at least ⅔ of I4C scientists contributing to CDE activities (Quantitative and qualitative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure engagement of stakeholders (see K3a,b) • Assess CDE KPIs and their measures (see Communication and Dissemination plan D7.1)
K6	Measure internal processes and functioning of project management structures, through interviews with selected scientists in the WPs where follow-up actions are published and internal processes are reassessed at the next project assessment stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informal interviews and/or anonymized surveys sent to project scientists (conducted by the PMO) • Publish follow-up actions via internal newsletter